

FRACTURE FIXATOR CONCEPT BASED ON SHAPE MEMORY POLYMER

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ABSTRACT

Shape Memory Polymers (SMPs) are polymeric smart materials that have the ability to return from temporary shape to their permanent shape included by an external stimulus, such as temperature change, PH, light, magnetic field and solution etc. Compared with the SMA, the SMPs have advantages of low density, easy processing, biodegradability, low cost, widely adjustable transition temperature, and large deformation. SMPs as a kind of active shape-changing and stimuli-responsive materials have seen rapid development. Due to their special functions, SMP has own broad application in biomedical field, mainly including tissue engineering, biological sutures, stents, bladder sensors and so on.

Traditionally, there are many kinds of fixator for fracture, such as plaster tablet, external fixations etc. However, generally, the tightness of the fixations for fracture treatments, such as plywood and plaster bandage, is difficult to control. As a consequence, it is easy to damage tissue and cause complications. So the fracture fixator based on SMP is developed for fracture. The tightness problem during different treatment stages can be effectively solved when using SMP, due to its variable stiffness and shape memory effects of SMP. Generally, injured limb is accompanied with swelling. During the treatment, the swelling goes down gradually as fracture heals, which results in losing of traditional fracture fixator. However, the adaptive repair device concept proposed in this paper can accomplish real-time adaption of the tightness according to the configuration of the injured limb. Therefore, the fixator has property of self-adaptability. When the injured limb becomes loose, applying thermo stimulus to fracture fixator, it can readjust to and remain the best fixed state. Besides, it can has several another advantages, such as, light-weight, easy to put, conforming to shape, x-ray transparent, easy disposal, provision of air-vents, etc. and more importantly some degree of adaptability to change shape and stiffness as the fracture healing progresses.

In this paper, the glass transition temperature of shape memory polymer (SMP) is firstly characterized by dynamic mechanical analyzer (DMA). The single/dual cantilever mode with geometric dimension 33.4mm*11.60mm*2.89mm is applied to investigate the basic mechanical properties (storage modulus, loss modulus and loss factor) of SMP under the temperature range from 25°C to 120°C. The glass transition temperatures are derived from the peak value of deviation of storage modulus, peak values of loss modulus and loss factor, the measured results demonstrate that the transition temperature from peak value of deviation of storage modulus and peak value of loss modulus are similar and significantly lower than the value from the peak value of loss factor. In addition, the effect of different heating rate (1°C/min, 2.5°C/min, 5°C/min) and different dynamic strain frequencies (1Hz, 5Hz, 9Hz, 13Hz) are considered to analyze the trend of glass transition temperature, the results show the glass transition temperature will nonlinear increase with the increasing of heating rate and strain frequencies.

Based on the glass transition temperature derived from the DMA experiments, a fracture fixator was fabricated. Before this, an arm of the volunteer was selected, and its size and shape was measured. The fixed plate circled around the finger exactly. The detailed usage process as follows: the prototype of fixator should be dipped into water higher than glass transition temperature before using

it. After the structure becomes soft, it is dried out, and then fixed into an arm. When the structure is cooled below glass transition temperature, the shape is preserved after releasing the outside pressure. During the fixed period, this structure exhibited good gas permeability and easy installation. It has provided an adequate support for arm and has shown a excellent fixing efficiency.

In this work, shape memory polymer fracture fixators are based on the feature of active deformation. The primary tests for application of the device are verified in both experimental and theoretical aspects. First, the mechanical properties and parameters were characterized and obtained from experiments.

Secondly, the thermal viscoelastic constitutive equation was established to stimulate the shape memory behavior of shape memory polymers. Through the comparison of experimental and theoretical results, the validity of theoretical model was verified, and deformation mechanism was explained. This study provides the theoretical and experimental support for the application of shape memory polymer in fracture fixation.

This work contains following aspects: (1) Isothermal uniaxial tensile, thermal stress relaxation and creep experiment tests were carried out to character the dynamic mechanical properties and static mechanical properties. The time-temperature equivalence equation was employed to determine the basic thermal viscoelastic material parameters. The changes of mechanical properties under cyclic loading were tested upon during load cycling experiments; the shape memory behavior of fracture fixations was studied through the experiments of shape memory cycle testing; (2) Correction the shape memory polymer viscoelastic constitutive equation was made. Recursive algorithm was used to compile Prony series constitutive equation into the UMAT subroutine, later based on that the ABAQUS software model was built to simulate the shape memory behavior; (3) The adaptive fracture fixation device based on the shape memory polymer was designed. Through uniaxial tensile test and the three-point bending test analysis, the tensile modulus, flexural modulus of the scale model structure, and tensile resilience, flexural restoring force were obtained, which provides data support for fracture fixation devices. By in vitro functional assays, the effect of fixing, and fixed demolition, adaptive feature and the feasibility of a shape memory polymer fracture fixation device, were verified.